

Industry 4.0 Conference: The impact of cognitive computing on the diagnostic process in the healthcare industry

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ABSTRACT

Automation threatens 25% of the jobs in the US and even more globally. Especially jobs that contain a lot of simple and repetitive tasks that no longer require intensive human labor. But can be done by computers. Intensive human labor is no longer required in the modern day knowledge economy (Annie Nove, 2019). Automation does not only have an increasingly bigger impact in low-skilled jobs, but it is also making its introduction in traditionally high-skilled jobs. Jobs like this are common to be found in the healthcare industry. Cognitive computing is the science branch that tries to let computers solve complex problems by mimicking the human brain's problem-solving skills. Cognitive computing is finding its way in different areas within the healthcare industry, specifically the diagnostic process. These diagnostic processes are continuously evolving to work more efficiently and accurately. This paper has a focus on the impact of cognitive computing on the medical diagnostic process.

KEYWORDS

Cognitive computing, diagnostic healthcare, conference publications

INTRODUCTION

Brief history of the diagnostic process

In the middle ages the medical diagnostic process followed the ideas of Hippocrates and

Galen to diagnose illnesses. Doctors believed that a person's humour had to be in balance. Each type of humour was matched to a season. Another way doctors carried out a medical diagnosis was by examining a person's urine. The doctors checked the color, smell and taste of a patient's urine (Mann, Lloyd, 1983).

By the Renaissance a new 'science of astrology was used to aid diagnosis, all twelve signs of the zodiac were linked to parts of the body. Doctors would determine the illness depending on what star sign you were born (Clark, 1979)

During the industrial period doctors started to be trained to carefully observe patients and symptoms for illnesses and diseases were printed in medical journals. this meant illnesses and diseases could be recognized by the symptoms of patients (Simon Szreter, 2004). In the late nineteenth and early twentieth century there was a rapid improvement in the science and technology concerning healthcare. This is also the time that the X-Ray machine first made its introduction. In the following thirty years it was extensively used to diagnose patients. In more modern times computers were used to diagnose patients with more detail using MRI scans. To detect more serious illnesses like cancer, blood tests were used. For more straightforward illnesses doctors still looked at the symptoms of the patients (Simon M, Mattson JS, 1996).

With the rise and fall of the dot-com bubble around the year 2000 the use of computers and the internet became widespread. Since more people have access to computers, the number of use cases raised exponential.

More people use computers and as a result, more and more applications and use cases for these computers are being invented (Thompson, Spanuth, 2018).

The medical sector is no exception. Software was developed to assist medical professionals to increase the accuracy and efficiency of their work. In the early days the software consisted mostly out of stand-alone applications but this was soon replaced by extensive ERP software packages aimed at the medical world (R.A Miller, 1994).

The next step in automation involved the use of cognitive computing. Cognitive computing, is a relatively new technology that will be implemented in the healthcare industry in the next couple of decades. The cognitive computing algorithms can be used to process an extensive amount of information and form a decision based on all relevant information. Today this is (mostly) done manually by the doctors. This new technology offers possibilities to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of the diagnostic process in the healthcare industry (L. Ogiela, 2010).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Within the healthcare industry the diagnostic process is an important aspect that is subject to human error because of the manual labor and knowledge that is required (M. Lyons et al, 2004).

The accuracy of a diagnostic process is important for the treatment plan of patients and therefore the overall health of the patients. An incorrect diagnosis could have serious health consequences and could eventually lead to the decease of a patient (M.L. Graber, 2013). Since computers are prone to making less errors than humans, the number of incorrect diagnosis could decline. Computers excel in performing a repetitive task in the same manner for unlimited times. Computers also excel in performing extremely complex calculations (J. H. Thompson, 1985)

In order to gain insights in the way cognitive computing can help diagnostic process within the healthcare industry, the following research question has been formulated: *'What is the impact of cognitive computing on the diagnostic process in the healthcare industry?'*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To determine the impact of cognitive computing on the diagnostic healthcare process, there are a few variables of importance.

Healthcare and automation

Investments in the healthcare sector made technologies as the X-ray and MRI widespread in developed countries. Up to 2010 more than 5 billion medical imaging examinations have been conducted worldwide (Roobottom, Morgan-Hughes, 2010).

This was a big step forward for automation in the healthcare. In the last century computers and automation found its way into every aspect of the diagnostic process in the healthcare and made sure that the efficiency and accuracy went up.

This, in combination with a variety of factors, is one of the reasons the life expectancy of humans rises (R. Gossink & J. Souquet, 2006).

Automation did not only have a big impact in the technology used to diagnose illnesses and diseases, it also had a big impact on the way data was processed by the help of information technology. Information technology has made it possible for health professionals to analyze large quantities of data. A lot of repetitive tasks which required human intervention could be automated using cognitive computing. Data automation involves:

- Extraction: relevant information is mined from multiple open data sources.
- Transformation: the data is converted into a machine-readable format.
- Loading: the data is then fed into the system to serve as the raw material for automation.

(C. Reddy & A. Sabharwal, 2014)

Big data is used in almost every sector, the health sector is no exception. With the help of big data analysis, the accuracy and precision of the diagnostic process has been improved in the last few years (W. Raghupathi, & V. Raghupathi, 2014).

Another technology used to improve the accuracy and precision of the diagnostic process is artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is the use of algorithms to emulate human intelligence in software. Artificial intelligence can help healthcare institutions to collect and transform patient data into meaningful information. This means complicated medical data can be analyzed by computer algorithms to approximate conclusions without any direct human input (K. Yu & A.L. Beam & I.S. Kohane, 2018).

Automation can not only be implemented in analyzing data but it could also be used to automate tasks traditionally done by hand. This is called Robotic Process Automation (M. Ratia, et al, 2018).

Cognitive computing

Cognitive computing is a sub-branch of computer sciences. The goal of cognitive computing is to simulate human thought processes in a self-learning algorithm to mimic the human brain. Computers are faster at making large amount of calculations, but they are not yet up to par compared to humans in understanding natural language, solving unique and complex problems.

Unique characteristics of cognitive computing:

- Adaptive: the algorithm changes as it learns new information in real time.
- Interactive: the algorithms are designed to interact with other devices, platforms and users.
- Iterative and stateful: they can define problems by asking additional questions or finding extra sources if the problem is ambiguous or incomplete. They remember previous interactions.
- Contextual: the algorithms understand contextual elements such as syntax, time, time and location.

(A.K. Noor, 2018).

The next step in healthcare automation

Since the diagnostic process in healthcare is a human task it is prone to making errors. Making errors in the diagnostic process can have a big impact on the overall health and life expectancy of a population. In the last decennium a certain trend can be perceived. Breast cancer is the most common form of cancer with it being 26.6% of all cancer diagnosis for women. This number is expected to rise with 11% in 2020 (Nederlandse Kankerregistratie, 2019).

Breast cancer diagnosis in most cases starts with the discovery of a lump in a woman's breast and goes to the general practitioner who will check the lump and verify if it is a lump. The general practitioner refers the patient to the hospital where a mammography and echography will be made. If

considered necessary an MRI scan will also be made. With each of the three processes the doctor checks the results and performs an analysis to see if the lump(s) of the patient have a potential high risk of breast cancer. Since the doctor is doing this manually this process is prone to human error. Cognitive computing can perform detailed comparisons between a huge amount of data. This relieves healthcare providers from their workload. (Davenport & Glover 2018)

Conceptual Model

Cognitive computing: is an independent variable which describes technology platforms that are broadly based on the scientific disciplines of artificial intelligence and signal processing. This is done by using automatic models to simulate the human thought process in complex situations where the answers can be ambiguous and uncertain.

Medical diagnostic process: is the dependent variable, because it may be influenced by the dependent variable 'cognitive computing'. This variable can take on differing values in response to IV manipulation. Diagnostic process is the entire process of information acquisition and processing for the purpose of providing assistance.

In the research question there are two variables of importance. To demonstrate the coherence and there by the relevance of these variables a graphic representation is made as shown by figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Hypotheses

Negative case analysis is important for the formulated hypotheses in this paragraph. Negative case analysis means that in all interviews the respondents have to agree on the subject in question. If all three subjects agree, H₁ can be assumed correct.

H₁: Cognitive computing has a positive effect on the diagnostic process.

Method

For this paper a qualitative research method has been chosen. This research is more descriptive in nature and focuses on the implementation of cognitive computing in the diagnostic process. To formulate an answer on the problem statement semi-structured interviews have been held with a general practitioner.

Before the interview relevant topics and general questions were chosen. In addition there was an interview schedule for preliminary research where deviations were allowed. This allows for the researcher(s) to ask further questions to clarify the respondents answers or to go more in depth about certain topics.

The second research question is answered by performing a literature study. The literature was selected by two criteria. The first criteria is quality, all used literature has to be of 'academic' quality. The term 'academic' refers to peer-reviewed and credible literature sources. In addition, the authors also have been analyzed by the amount of citations and publications to audit the source.

The second criteria is that the paper has to be relevant and connected to the terms of cognitive computing and diagnostic process. These terms will serve als keywords while searching for academic papers. Table 1 is created with related terms and synonyms to broaden the search options. The exact keywords used in the research can be found in the appendix.

RESULTS

WHAT IS THE CURRENT DIAGNOSTIC PROCESS IN THE HEALTHCARE?

The diagnostic process is a complex process. The General practitioner gives a prognostic advice based on the symptoms, causes and the patient's disease history. In the diagnostic process the doctor must be able to label the symptoms, classify illness, and choose specific treatments over other treatments to help the patient.

The diagnostic process can be split into two areas, the first sub-area applies to groups for which diagnostic criteria apply. These are patients with a specific disease that show obvious symptoms.

The second sub-area contains patients for whom a real diagnostic process is needed. The patients show individual symptoms and details that cannot be categorized. In this process the doctor looks for both generalities and for specific and idiosyncratic choices. The doctor claims that during this process there are always certain points, symptoms of symptoms that reveal what treatment is needed for

that specific illness.

In the second sub-area the doctor starts the process by working through clustered characters or the patient's story. This results in one or two possible diagnoses that could possibly be the solution to the patient's problem. This is also referred to as the implementation phase. After this phase, the doctor starts checking the diagnosis by performing specific tests. This is also called the deductive phase. Each of the two phases requires its own specific work strategy and both phases are essential for diagnostic work.

Cognitive computing can play a role in the second area of patients where the symptoms cannot be categorized directly. The doctor must then offer a solution based on experience, personal working methods and knowledge play an important role here. Cognitive computing can contribute to this decision-making process.

What is the effect of cognitive computing in the diagnostics process?

Cognitive computing uncovers new insights by enabling researchers to discover relationships among genes, proteins, diseases, pathways and phenotypes. Doctors can identify critical attributes of patients with the help of cognitive computing. They can provide easy to read rappsorts for patients. the algorithms used can also provide detailed and specific diagnostic to healthcare providers. Since this is all done automatically the chance of human errors decreases drastically. The use of cognitive computing within healthcare is still in a very early phase. It has only been used in clinical trials to optimize patient selection and recruitment. However the real power of cognitive computing is assisting in creating personalized treatment plans. This optimizes the patient experience and enhances the accuracy and efficiency of the diagnostic process by as much as 50% found in studies (A. Gudivada & N. Tabrizi, 2018, S. Gaglio & G. Lo re, 2019).

Aside from these benefits there is also a 50% reduction of hospitalization costs. Cognitive computing can be used in two methods within the healthcare sector. The first one is that it can be used for knowledge-driven Decision Support Systems assisted by cognitive computing. A knowledge-driven decision support system is a business intelligence tool customized to meet the needs and requirements of an organization. The main focus is on identifying knowledge sharing and distribution needs of an organization (A. Gudivada & N. Tabrizi, 2018, S. Gaglio & G. Lo re, 2019).

This type of method can be used in healthcare

sector to support hospitals and other healthcare providers but does benefit in the diagnostic process itself.

The second method cognitive computing can be used is through data-driven Decision Support System. This system searches and compares for patterns that have been previously entered into the system that are known symptoms of certain diseases. A data driven Decision Support System uses the health data to support making decisions within the diagnostic process based on the available data (Aberdeen Group, 1995).

The footprint of medical data is expected to increase exponentially, by 2020 the data will double every 73 days. The fast majority, roughly 80%, will be unstructured data. With the help of cognitive computing this large volume of data can be analyzed and applied in ways that are meaningful for patients. In addition to this also the amount of medical research, clinical trials and treatment options are continuously rising. It is not possible for healthcare providers to keep up to date with all new information and knowledge that is created in their specific field (A. Gudivada & N. Tabrizi, 2018, S. Gaglio & G. Lore, 2019).

Cognitive computing is based on machine learning, this means that the computer algorithms are not programmed to do something but they are taught to do something. Cognitive computers continuously acquire knowledge by analyzing data. This is not done with traditional rule-based algorithms but the system itself looks for patterns. By processing the data this way the system creates its own models and solutions, this is the self-learning part based on machine learning. Cognitive computing however goes one step further and uses neuralistic programming to mimic the human brain.

Cognitive computing is being used in various artificial intelligence applications. The purpose of cognitive computing is to create automatic information technology that can solve problems without any human assistance

However, the greatest disruption proceed from the attendance of cognitive computing occurs probably in the healthcare sector. The new AI systems that adopt the of doctors will increase accessibility and reduce costs and, above all, improve the quality of the results (S. N. Bini, 2018)

CONCLUSION

Based on the data collected by interviewing the general practitioner it can be concluded that cognitive computing will have a big impact within the diagnostic process. More specifically, in the second sub-area of the diagnostic process where the symptoms of patients cannot be directly categorized. The general practitioner must offer a solution based on experience, personal working methods and knowledge. Cognitive computing can contribute to this decision-making process, possibly assisted by knowledge-driven decision support systems.

Additional literature can conclude that the use of cognitive computing within healthcare is still in an early phase of its life cycle. The real power of cognitive computing is to assist in creating personalized treatment plans. This optimizes the patient experience and enhances the accuracy and efficiency of the diagnostic process. Cognitive computing can also be used through data-driven Decision Support System. This system uses an algorithm that searches for known patterns which have been previously entered into the system that are known symptoms of certain diseases.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1 searching words

preliminary research		
Concept #1	Concept #2	Concept #3
Cognitive computing	Diagnostic process	Privacy
Self-learning technologies	Healthcare system	Privacy policy
Decision-making support	Healthcare processes	Private life
Cognitive systems	Process healthcare	Privacy breach
Cognitive computers	Signaling and diagnostics	Personal freedom
Industry 4.0	Medical diagnosis	Laws of privacy
Edge computing	Diagnostic process (healthcare)	
	Process healthcare system	